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PRIMARY SCHOOL PSYCHOLOGY AND ITS ROLE IN STUDENT EDUCATION

Annotation: *This article illustrates child psychology, the importance of pedagogical and psychological skills in the education of primary school students, the most important aspects of student life.*

Keywords: *Psychology, child psychology, temperament, upbringing, mental process.*

Human psychology is important at any age due to its complexity. One of like these is the school period. The reason is that at this time the same character (temperament) of children is formed. Even a little exaggeration can lead to a radical change in upbringing and lifestyle of the child.

It is well-known that primary education is the most complex stage of the education system in almost all countries of the world. This is because it is the most important integral part of general secondary education, and its foundation is primary education, which includes the first and fourth grades. Which way children take in the future (good or bad) depends on the education and upbringing they receive during this period. It is at this time that the child's psychological temperament begins to change. Managing child psychology is easy in the elementary grades, and a teacher with strong psychological knowledge can turn it in the direction he or she wants. However, if you pay close attention, it's called child psychology management. This is not to say that psychology is simple, easy.

“Child psychology is a branch of psychology that studies the general and specific features of children's psychological development, how this process takes place at different stages of life, the forces and laws that drive it. For this reason, child psychology is often called as youth psychology. This child psychology learns to form as the emergence and development of mental processes (cognitive, verbal, emotional, volitional, etc.) in children, the determination of mental characteristics, the development of various activities (games, reading, work), the child's personality. Child

psychology uses research methods developed in general psychology. However, there are some peculiarities of its use. Cross-sections and various studies are used to study a child's age.”[1]

In the first case, only one mental process is studied in children belonging to different age groups at the same time. In the second case, the mental characteristics of a particular (selected) child are studied over many years. This, in turn, allows them to monitor the overall development of the psyche.

"Temperament is a set of unstable personality traits that express a person's activity, speed of behavior, and emotional side" [2]. From this definition, the temperaments of preschoolers and primary school students and learners are not yet fully formed. With regard to temperament traits, they are still present in the student.

Almost everyone goes through primary education. Not a single child in this period has even preferred the words of his/her teacher to the words of their parents. If a parent says that to a child, “No, you don't know”, they insist that our teacher said that. During this time, every word the teacher says becomes a piece of information that the child will remember for a lifetime (perhaps when he or she learns the truth about a misunderstood concept). From these data, to sum up, the psychological upbringing of the child (positive or negative) is primarily the responsibility of the teacher.

In our modern life, if we look more closely at our lives, we can see that the students in the primary grades have different behaviors. Some children are polite, modest, hardworking, enterprising, intelligent, knowledgeable, while others are aggressive, rebellious, angry, and so on. If this situation is closely studied, these positive children are usually in the same class and the negative ones are in the same class. A group of students in the same class is taught and educated by a particular teacher. It means that in the division into the above characteristic classes, a good knowledge of child psychology and its good upbringing determines the pedagogical and psychological level of the teacher. The lexical meaning of upbringing is: practical pedagogical process aimed at formation; It is a set of measures taken to ensure that a person acquires the qualities necessary for life in society.”[3].

Forming a team in the primary grades, namely, bringing them together into a cohesive team, also requires psychological skills. First of all, the teacher should study the students from the first grade on the basis of various pedagogical methods. This process is required to continue not only at the beginning, but until the child completes 4th grade. The reason is that the loss of control between grades 1-4 will lead to big changes. For example, a child may start stealing, a high-ranking bully may be jealous of children, sneer at them, learn to lie, fail to prepare for class, and even reduce attendance. This requires the control of the student, using both pedagogical and psychological potential. The only example is the pedagogical method of dialogue with the student, which can be determined at certain intervals for upbringing of the child and find solutions to the problem will be a psychological method.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in the process of education, not only knowledge but also education should be carried out along with it, especially in the period of primary education, the interest of students in the lessons is worthy of the next stages of education. Moreover, it is the most pressing issue in educating students. Every knowledge and education given by a teacher in this process is very valuable. That`s why it takes a lot of effort on the part of the educator. By repeating this process over and over again, the teacher's skills will improve.

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